

HEPHAESTUS

**Heritage in Europe: New technologies in
craft for preserving and innovating futures**

Project No. 101095123

Deliverable 5.1

**Report on establishment of the network of
municipalities, heritage sites and museums
participating at the Living Lab**

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Executive Summary

This document provides a comprehensive overview of the Hephæstus project's goal and related actions to establish a network of municipalities, heritage sites, and museums participating in the Green Living Lab – one of the key outputs of the Hephæstus project. On this premise, the document focuses on the Living Lab principles, the context of Bornholm, and the Hephæstus project craft ecosystems.

The Hephæstus project, initiated in 2023, aims to establish a Living Lab in Bornholm, Denmark, integrating sustainable craft and circular economy principles with practical experiments on new craft-related products, services, and technologies. The document outlines the EU context, the project's objectives, and the relevance of Living Labs to promote circular economy in the European craft sector.

Bornholm, a Danish island with a population of 39,000 constitutes a rich craft ecosystem. BOFA, the waste management authority, aligns with Bornholm's vision to become waste-free by 2032. The craft community, designated as a World Craft Region, has experienced growth, collaboration, and economic benefits.

Living Labs are defined as temporary arenas designed for user and stakeholder engagement in ongoing innovative development projects. The document elaborates on the five essential principles of Living Labs and their iterative life cycle. It also highlights BOFA's past experience with Living Labs, specifically in the Wasteman project, focusing on sustainable waste systems.

The document outlines some of the key activities undertaken within the Hephæstus project to establish the network of municipalities, heritage sites and museums participating at the Living Lab, namely:

- **Stakeholder Analysis:** A thorough analysis of Bornholm's craft ecosystem stakeholders is presented, outlining their positions and relationships concerning the Hephæstus project.
- **Risk Analysis:** Potential challenges and preventive actions are identified, covering aspects like collaboration issues, stakeholder interest, and craft makers' involvement.
- **Communication:** Various communication strategies, including online and offline channels, have been implemented to inform and engage stakeholders.
- **Activities for the First 6 Months:** The document details the initial steps, including the call for craft ambassadors, kick-off events in Venice and Bassano del Grappa, and a stakeholder event on Bornholm.

- **The Established Network Towards the Living Lab:** The Maker's Island Secretariat plays a pivotal role in maintaining the craft ecosystem network. Continuous meetings and collaboration are emphasized for success.
- **Future Expansion of the Network:** The Living Lab's envisioned expansion includes both Bornholm's craft ecosystem and collaboration within the Hephæstus consortium, fostering dialogue and knowledge exchange.

Future activities are outlined to develop the Living Lab, expand the network, and achieve project objectives, emphasizing collaboration between ecosystems and consortium partners.

Envisioned challenges include mobilizing the well-established craft ecosystem, addressing concerns about project utilization, and avoiding a top-down approach. Careful interaction with stakeholders is crucial to overcoming resistance.

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
CC	Creative Commons
DCMI	Dublin Core™ Metadata Initiative
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2022	Horizon 2022
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
PID	Persistent and unique Identifier
QDA	Qualitative Data Analysis
V	Version
WP	Work Package

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Partners acronyms

Copenhagen Business School	CBS
Gooteborgs Universitet	UGOT
Universita degli Studi di Roma Tor Vergata	UTOV
Bornholms Regionskommune	BOFA
Fablab Venezia srl	FABLAB VE
Universita Ca' Foscari Venezia	UNIVE
Comune Di Bassano Del Grappa	CBDG
Wit Berry	WIT
Frodska-parsetur Foroya	SETUR
Confartigianato Vicenza	CONFARTIG VI
Cna Veneto Ovest	CAN VENETO

1. Introduction

1.1 About HEPHAESTUS

The overarching ambition of HEPHAESTUS is to bring together cutting-edge technologies with traditional craft to co-create solutions in the form of a suite of tools, methodologies, and business models to make the future of European craft ecosystems socially, culturally, environmentally, and economically sustainable. HEPHAESTUS will test and evaluate solutions co-created across five regional craft ecosystems within a “Future of Craft” Green Living Lab situated in Bornholm, a Danish Island and regional municipality given the title of World Craft Region. Ultimately, the project sets out to create a sustainable network (especially including regional realities) of heritage sites, cultural and creative sectors, institutions, universities, local, regional and national authorities, enterprises, and other relevant stakeholders engaged in preservation of craft heritage that will take the project’s results, further adapt and deploy them in a broader range of craft ecosystems, and ensure a long- lasting legacy of the HEPHAESTUS project.

The creation of the first “Future of Craft” action-oriented Living Lab constitutes a key objective of the HEPHAESTUS project. An engaging space designed to involve relevant and local stakeholders and interested parties for testing HEPHAESTUS results and diffusing the circular craft-driven design innovation methodology as well as the frameworks and theories developed in the project. Based on the principles of New European Bauhaus, the Lab will facilitate the creation of bridges between disciplines and sustainable approaches through a think tank, and will steer the transformation of craft ecosystems along three key values: sustainability – from climate goals and Sustainable Development Goals to circularity, zero pollution, and preservation of biodiversity; aesthetics – which includes form and shape, quality of the object, but also quality of the experience that craft can provide, linked to the experiential tourism economy; and inclusion – from valuing diversity to securing accessibility and affordability.

1.2 About this document

This document aims at explaining and contextualising how this project is approaching establishment of the network of municipalities, heritage sites and museums participating at the Future of Craft” Green Living Lab. This document is structured as follows - it begins with a detailed introduction to the Living Labs and their operating principles, cooperation with crafts people and BOFA's experience of working with Living Labs. This is followed by a description of the Danish Island of Bornholm, which is home to BOFA and a large number of craftspeople, and where the aforementioned green Living Lab will be established. The networking approach will subsequently be discussed together with stakeholder and risk analysis and with a description of the activities undertaken so far and the current and future challenges.

2. Living Labs: definition and cases

2.1 Definition of Living Lab

A Living Lab is a temporary well-known arena or environment that is created to involve and co-create with users and relevant actors and stakeholders in an ongoing innovative development project. A Living Lab can be used to develop and test new technologies and solutions in a familiar setting, get new insights and discover new opportunities and solutions in a given time frame, involve users and relevant actors in a co-design process, experiment with new technologies and solutions, and evaluate and validate the technologies and/or solutions that are being tested. A Living Lab is built on five essential principles of value, influence, sustainability, openness, and realism, as shown in the 5-star figure below (figure 1) (Femmer et al, 2019).

Figure 1: A Living Lab's five essential principles (Femmer et al, 2019, p. 27)

A Living Lab is structured around iterations around a life cycle that includes the phases of contextualization, concretization, implementation, and feedback. In the phase of contextualization, relevant technologies and respondents are investigated and looked into which ones should be included in the Living Lab. The concretization phase is about defining

the baseline for the project and Living Lab and identifying central users and stakeholders to be included. In the implementation phase, new technologies are tested with the users and stakeholders. The feedback phase is where evaluating measurements and interactions happens with the technology (Femmer et al, 2019). It is important to notice that the activities within the Living Lab are iterative.

2.2 Living Lab and Craft Communities

BOFA is responsible for establishing a Future of Craft Green Living Lab on Bornholm together with craft communities. The goal is to use the Living Lab as a "Green Bauhaus" where sustainable tourism and circular economy is connected to practical experiments of new services, technologies and business models around the future of craft. The solutions developed in the project will be tested with the principles of circular economy. The Living Lab will be established and ready to test new solutions and technologies in March 2025.

2.3 Past experience with Living Labs

In 2019-2021 BOFA was a partner in the EU-funded (Interreg South Baltic + European Regional Development Fund) project, Wasteman. The goal with Wasteman was to develop and integrate a sustainable waste system to ensure efficient recycling of waste, based on principles from circular economy and in accordance with European Union regulations. BOFA developed, designed and tested new sorting- and handling solutions for household waste on Bornholm, whereas the goal was to contribute to BOFA's vision of a waste-free island by 2032 (see chapter 3.2). BOFA carried out a high degree of citizen involvement, in order to anchor new sorting habits and waste systems. The process included testing new solutions in Living Labs, which were carried out in selected trial areas in the towns of Gudhjem and Pedersker in the summer of 2020. The citizens were involved through different design thinking and co-design/create methods, where a number of events and workshops (Figure 2) together with designers, architects, engineers, urban planners, researchers, etc.

Figure 2: Workshops with citizens in project Wasteman

The design process with the citizens led to new ideas on how to collect waste in the two towns, what the collection points should look like, what kind of fractions that should

be collected etc., whereas different prototypes (Figure 2) were developed to test the solutions in real life-settings in the Living Labs.

Figure 3: Waste collection prototype

The knowledge and outcome from the Wasteman, project can be used in BOFA's future work with establishing waste collection points for household waste on Bornholm.

3. Bornholm and the vision for a Living Lab at BOFA

3.1 The Island

Bornholm is a small Danish island located in the Baltic Sea close to the Swedish coast (Figure 4). Bornholm has approximately 39.000 inhabitants and is a popular tourist destination with over 500.000 visitors per year, whereas a large portion of the economy is geared towards this. The main city on Bornholm is Rønne. In order to reach Bornholm from the rest of Denmark it is possible to take a 1,5-hour ferry ride from Ystad (Sweden) to Rønne, a 5,5-hour ferry ride from Køge (Denmark) to Rønne, or a 30 minutes flight from Copenhagen Airport to Bornholm's Airport in Rønne.

Figure 4: Map that indicates Bornholm's position in the Baltic Sea

3.2 BOFA and the Regional Municipality of Bornholm

BOFA is the solid waste management authority and service provider on the island, under the direct control of the Regional Municipality of Bornholm. BOFA was established in 1986 and consists today of recycling centers, a landfill, and a waste incineration plant. BOFA treats annually approximately 80.000 metric tonnes waste, where approximately 65% is recycled, 28% is incinerated, and 7% is disposed (Christensen et al, 2021).

What distinguishes Bornholm and BOFA is its highly ambitious vision of “*Bornholm showing the way – without waste 2032*” (BOFA, 2019), where the waste incineration plant will be decommissioned and all waste will be treated as resources that can be recirculated in an infinity loop (Christensen et al, 2021).

In 2008, the Regional Municipality of Bornholm implemented the vision of a Bright Green Island (Bornholms Regionskommune, 2018), where Bornholm strategically will

work towards a greener and transition to a 100% sustainable and climate-friendly island in 2035 by targeting eight sustainability goals:

- Bornholm turns sustainability into good business.
- Bornholm keeps accounts of the green transition.
- Bornholm will at any-time be a role model for a climate-friendly community.
- Bornholm runs green on land.
- Bornholm links sustainability and housing with a cultural identity.
- Bornholm is a beacon for sustainable Danish food.
- Bornholm makes its natural wealth a part of the bottom line.
- When I'm on Bornholm, I'm part of 'Bright Green Island'." (Bornholms Regionskommune, 2018, p. 7).

3.3 The Craft Community

Bornholm's underground consists of different kinds of raw materials such as granite, sandstone, gravel, coal, clay and kaolin which has formed the basis for some of the most important industries on the Island. Jars and pots from Bornholm were sold throughout the Baltic Sea area already in the middle age, and in the 1900s a number of small craft enterprises arose ([Bornholms Kunstmuseum, Kunsthåndværk](#)). Today, Bornholm can be seen as a well-established craft ecosystem that consist of more than hundred craft makers within textile, metal, ceramic, glassblowing and woodcarving, museums, galleries, craft collectives, Maker's Island, Arts & Crafts Association Bornholm and the Danish Royal Academy of glass and ceramics (Center for Regional- og Turismeforskning, 2023).

Bornholm got the title of World Craft Region in 2017, which was enabled due to the preparations made by the Arts & Crafts Association Bornholm (ACAB) – a association that consist of local professional makers. In 2019, the Regional Municipality of Bornholm (BRK) established a steering committee for the World Craft Region initiative and the secretariate of "Maker's Island" was formed. The steering committee's and secretariate's goal is to achieve local development and growth within the craft sector. An evaluation by Bornholm's Centre for Regional and Tourism Research has for example shown that the employment within craftsmanship on the island has increased by 31 percentage from 2017 to 2022 and that the income of employed/self-employed people in the craft sector has grown by 26% from 2019 to 2022 (Center for Regional- og Turismeforskning, 2023). Due to several Maker's Island initiatives the collaboration across the craft ecosystem has been strengthened which has led to new cross-sector collaborations on the island within skill development, education, communication, business development etc. The title of World Craft Region and the work of Maker's Island has made craft important for the tourism industry and the overall branding of Bornholm, which has had a benefit on Bornholm's economy. Furthermore, there have been an increase in the number of applications to the Royal Academy's international glass and ceramic school on Bornholm, and the synergies between the school and the established craft makers on the island has been strengthened, whereas more of the school's students choose to stay at the island after graduating (Center for Regional- og Turismeforskning, 2023).

3.4 Opportunities and objectives for the Hephaestus Living Lab

By being a partner in Hephæstus, BOFA will get the opportunity to facilitate new collaborations across the craft sector on Bornholm to support the transition to a circular economy and increase the resource utilization for the benefit of Bornholm and the vision of becoming waste free by 2032.

4. Approaches for establishing a network

4.1 Stakeholder Analysis

A stakeholder analysis of the craft ecosystem of Bornholm (figure 2) has been carried out in order to get an overview of the different stakeholders and their position regarding Hephæstus. The stakeholder analysis has been used in communication activities to spread knowledge about Hephæstus and BOFA's and Bornholm's role in the project, and to get an idea of whom to interact with regarding the establishment of the network.

Figure 5: Stakeholder analysis of the craft ecosystem on Bornholm

4.2 Risk Analysis

A risk analysis has been carried out in order to get an overview of possible things that can go wrong and the different preventive actions that can be applied.

What can go wrong	Consequences 1-5	Probability 1-5	Risk (K*S)	Preventive actions
Challenging collaboration with Maker's Island Secretariat – conflicts of interest may arise.	4	3	12	Communication and involvement from start to finish. Close formal collaboration.
The stakeholders are not interested in the Living Lab.	5	2	10	Continuous communication and involvement. Co-design/creation of the Living Lab.
No interest among craft makers in using new technologies – conflicts of interest and/or understanding may arise between craft makers and the project.	4	2	8	Communication and workshops.
No interest among craft makers in developing and implementing more sustainable and circular business models.	4	2	8	Communication and workshops.
The craft makers do not see the benefits of being part of the project – the craft makers may ask questions as to why a waste company should run the project on Bornholm, which might lead to conflicts.	5	1	5	Communication, and early and continuous involvement.

Table 1: Risk analysis

4.3 Communication

As seen in table 2 different forms of communication were carried out in order to inform stakeholders about the project and to prevent the risks described in the risk analyses (chapter 4.2).

Communication		
Where	Target group	When
Hephæstus description on BOFA's website	Wide	April 2023
Initial meetings with Maker's Island Secretariat	Secretariat	Continuously (Minimum ones a month)
Call for crafts maker (Maker's Island' facebookpage and email-list)	Craft makers	March 2023
Initial meetings with interested craft makers	Craft makers	March-April 2023
Info-meeting	Craft makers	April 2023
Hephæstus post on BOFA Vision 2023 facebookpage	Wide	May 2023
Continuously meetings with craft ambassadors and craft makers	Craft makers	Continuously (Minimum ones a month with craft ambassadors)
Participating in relevant vernissages to network	Craft ecosystem and interested stakeholders/actors	Continuously
Meeting with Bornholm' Museum	Bornholm' Museum	June 2023
Visit and talks with the different museums	Museums	May, June, and August 2023
Invitation to event on traditional craft/Hephæstus	Stakeholders from stakeholder analysis	Juli 2023
Event	Stakeholders from stakeholder analysis	August 2023

Table 2: Communication activities carried out in T5.1

5. Establishing the network participating at the Living Lab

5.1 Activities for the first 6 months

Call for craft ambassadors

Several meetings with Maker's Island Secretariat have been conducted since February 2023 in order to get them in the loop of the project and find synergies between their work and Hephæstus.

Maker's Island can be seen as a gate-keeper to the network of craft makers and relevant stakeholders within the craft ecosystem on Bornholm, whereas they have helped BOFA with sending out a call for craft ambassadors. The call was sent out on Maker's Island Facebook page (Figure 6) and to an internal email-list on March 7th 2023, and spread mouth-to-mouth on Maker's Island steering committee meeting and the Arts & Craft Association Bornholm's yearly meeting. The call was noticed by several craft makers, and several individual meetings were held face-to-face. The call got four serious respondents from four different ceramicist, whom are now representing Bornholm's ecosystem as craft ambassadors.

Figure 6: Call for craft ambassadors on Maker's Island's Facebook page

In connection with the call, the four craft ambassadors were asked to engage with the artist group from D20 Art Lab when they visited the island to capture the atmosphere of craft. Following D20 Art Labs' visit, the four craft ambassadors got the opportunity to get more knowledge about the project and give insights and their perception to what the atmosphere of craft on Bornholm consist of. This also provided a great opportunity to initiate conversations with the craft ecosystem on Bornholm.

Kick-off event in Venice and Bassano del Grappa

Related to the Hephæstus kick-off in Venice and Bassano del Grappa, an info-meeting with the craft ambassadors were held to discuss their role at the kick-off and in the project, and to get the logistics in place.

From May 24th to May 28th 2023 three out of four craft ambassadors from Bornholm (Figure 7) travelled to Venice and Bassano del Grappa to participate in the kick-off and to meet craft ambassadors from the Swedish and Italian ecosystems, as well as the rest of the consortium partners.

On day one, craft ambassadors showcased the craft ecosystems of the Hephæstus project, illustrating the diverse and innovative approaches taken to preserve and advance traditional crafts within their respective ecosystems.

On day two, craft ambassadors visited Fablab Venezia while a workshop addressing two tracks: - "CRAFTS & BUSINESS" and "CRAFTS, SOCIETY & SUSTAINABILITY." - was held at University of Ca' Foscari.

The Kick-off served as opportunity for knowledge assimilation, with participants sharing insights, observations, and takeaways from a series of presentations, debates and informal discussions, with the aim of catalysing further dialogue and potential collaborations among attendees. Moreover, this proved as a useful first experiment to collect feedback, understand and align expectations with the ecosystem ambassadors involved in the project.

The travel reinforced the collaboration and relationship between BOFA and Bornholm craft ambassadors, as well as provided a good baseline to further develop the network of ambassadors across ecosystems, the feedback collected pointed towards two opportunities for further improvements:

1) Ecosystem ambassadors expressed their willingness to be actively involved in future academic workshops in order to positively benefit from ongoing knowledge exchange between researchers in the field of craft and creative industries, as well as to be up to date with project ongoing and future possible activities.

2) Danish and Ecosystem ambassadors expressed the need willingness to interact more closely to the Italian ecosystem, as the latter was mainly involved in the plenary sessions concerning the presentation of the ecosystems, while did not actively participate in the activities organised in the City of Venice.

Figure 7: Group picture from Bassano del Grappa of three craft ambassadors and the two project managers from BOFA

Stakeholder event on Bornholm

An event was carried out August 15th 2023 with the purpose to present relevant stakeholders for Hephæstus, the Living Lab concept and best-practice cases. Participants within the Bornholm craft ecosystem, encompassing craft ambassadors, Maker's Island, Arts & Craft Association Bornholm, Hjort' Fabric, The Royal Danish Academy and various local businesses attended the event.

The event provided the opportunity to spark conversations about the project and slowly start the co-design process of the Living Lab. A workshop session helped create a deeper understanding of the craft sector on Bornholm and the challenges they face, as well as gave them the opportunity to make wishes for the project and the future of craft on Bornholm. Furthermore, the event helped to ensure that the stakeholders felt heard and that they have an influence on the project and Living Lab on Bornholm. The event ended with a tour around BOFA to see the recycling center and the incineration plant (Figure 8). The event program is presented in the appendix.

Figure 8: Tour at BOFA

The participants were separated in two groups of five doing the workshop session to ensure more intimate discussions where everybody had the opportunity to speak. The groups were provided with post-it notes and pens to write down notes, thoughts and keywords (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Workshop sessions

The first workshop activity tried to make the participants map challenges in the craft ecosystem. To this activity the groups were provided with a worksheet and an envelope with examples of keywords, such as “technologies, economic sustainability, collaborations etc.” to generate conversations (Figure 9). These keywords were gathered through meetings with stakeholders from the ecosystem. Several challenges were mentioned as seen in table 3.

Keywords	Challenges
Economic sustainability	Hard to make a living, as the craft makers only sell in the summer time – it might be easier to be a craft maker in e.g., Copenhagen Hard to get funds, whereas projects die
Advertisement (in connection to economic sustainability)	Difficult to do storytelling about the production and pricing Not easy to do advertisement and it often comes last – it is easier when you have a gallery or a place “Scared” of over-branding themselves Difficult to get out in the world – how to be visible? Difficult to be visible and sell from October to May
Sustainability in regards to the environment and climate	All resources are imported How to define or re-define quality when a product is made from reused material – how to price the product?
Social sustainability	Difficult to maintain a good/healthy work/life-balance
New technologies	Don’t know how to use new technologies – new technologies are not prioritized Don’t have time to learn new technologies Clay and computer are not a good match

Table 3: Challenges mapped by stakeholders from the craft ecosystem on Bornholm

The second workshop activity were about the participants’ wishes (table 4) for the future of craft on Bornholm and the outcome of Hephæstus and how it can target some of the mapped challenges. To this activity the groups were provided with a worksheet

where they could place post-it notes and write down keynotes. The participants' wishes can be used in other relevant WPs and to target Living Lab activities on Bornholm. The participants mentioned a concern regarding the diversity of the four ecosystems (Bornholm, Dals Långed, Venice and Bassano del Grappa) and how the project expect to collaborate with the ecosystem on Bornholm and how to ensure that the innovations, solutions, technologies fit into the Living Lab.

The project of Hephæstus should...
...provide advertisement-courses for craft makers
...provide collaborations with Copenhagen Business School students to help craft makers with advertisement and branding
...provide courses in business development for creative businesses
...pay for the craft makers' time spend on the project
...help with funding
...provide interns from the different university-partners
...generate new knowledge about sustainability and technologies
...facilitate new collaborations
...find connections with already existing projects (World Craft Council)
...provide new knowledge on recycling, reuse etc. to the craft makers
...provide money to buy new equipment
...get craft on the political agenda
...develop and provide workshops in using crushed glass, ceramics etc.
...courses on how to produce sustainable
...accommodate the joint efforts already existing on Bornholm
...make a formalized collaboration with Maker's Island Secretariat on Bornholm
...cooperate with craft week on Bornholm
...provide a shared digital platform (online store) for craft on Bornholm
...provide the Royal Academy of glass and ceramics with new education forms and knowledge developed in Hephæstus
...make sure not to apply a top-down approach
...ask the craft makers what the project should solve

Table 4: Wishes for the project of Hephæstus mapped by the craft ecosystem on Bornholm

5.2 The established network towards the Living Lab

Through several communication activities, research and by engaging with the craft ecosystem on Bornholm, described in chapter 4 and 5, it has become evident that there is already a well-established network consisting of relevant stakeholders to include in the Living Lab.

The Maker's Island Secretariat plays a crucial role in creating and maintaining this already established network consisting of craft makers, associations (Arts and Crafts Association Bornholm), museums, schools and SMEs, as described in chapter 3.3 and 5.1.

It is important to involve the whole network in the Living Lab at some point in the design process in order for solutions to be tested in a real-life setting. However, the stakeholder analysis has shown that the Maker's Island Secretariat and Arts and Crafts Association Bornholm (ACAB) is essential to include in the project for it to be successful. Thereby, it is important to have continuously meetings and talks to find synergies and work together in order to offer the network the best possible outcomes, overcome some of the challenges in the ecosystem and target the ecosystem's wishes to the project and future of craft on Bornholm. It is key that the project does not have a top-down approach on the established network.

5.3 Future expansion of the network of actors involved & expected modes of participation

The activities conducted in the first six months of the project constitutes the baseline to further develop the Living Lab and expand the network of actors involved throughout the process. On this basis, future activities will be developed consistently with Objective 5 of the project - Establish a green living lab for testing the HEPHAESTUS innovations. ^[L]_{SEP} The envisioned Green living Lab is conceived as a space to share HEPHAESTUS results and diffuse the craft-driven design innovation methodology developed throughout the project. In this regard, the expansion of the network of actors involved in the green living lab will not only result from the enrolment of Bornholm relevant stakeholders (Figure 2), but also from the convergence of research and action-oriented activities across all the craft ecosystems and Workpackages involved in the project. Hence, future expansion of the network will occur across two main levels:

Within Bornholm

As the network and craft ecosystem is already well-established on Bornholm, it may be transgressive for the stakeholders and actors being part of this network if a third actor as BOFA might interfere and disturb the already joint efforts. To expand the network, BOFA can facilitate new collaborations across relevant stakeholders (Figure 2) through dedicated events concerning future developments of the Green Living Lab. On the same line, BOFA will host one project meeting in the third year of the project where all relevant partners from the consortium will engage in close contact with the Bornholm craft ecosystem to share and discuss preliminary project results. ^[L]_{SEP}

From Hephaestus consortium towards Bornholm

As a space to The Green Living Lab is meant to facilitate the creation of bridges between disciplines and sustainable approaches, as well as its dissemination across the Bornholm community, including, but not limiting to, the city craft ecosystem. This will be taken into account into the development of Hephaestus project research activities and co-design work. Figure 10 provides an overview of ten future activities which will contribute to the establishment of the network participating at the Green Living Lab. The activities included in the picture refer to participatory events (i.e. open to the community of one or more craft ecosystems) or project meetings (i.e. limited to Hephaestus consortium) specifically planned to contribute to one or more project objectives, and which lead to the results constituting the offer of the Green Living Lab. In particular, activities 1, 4 and 8 refer to participatory moments in the form of Craft workshops or Design Thinking Workshops with craftmakers and other relevant stakeholders which will be organised to achieve the objective of developing new sustainable business models for the craft sector. Activities 2, 3, 7 and 9 refer to both project meetings and participatory events which will be designed to define, develop and test the craft-driven innovation methodology. Activity 5 refers to the opening of the Green Living Lab, which will occur by March 2025, after two years of project activities and preparation. The latter will be followed by a Craft conference for craft-maker associations and cluster of EU funded projects on Crafts, whereby results achieved and expected project outcomes will be discussed with relevant stakeholders in Brussels. Activity 10 constitutes the final Exhibition held in Bornholm about the future of Craft, whereby project results will be presented to and discussed with the Bornholm Community.

5.4 Current and future challenges

The already well-established network and craft ecosystem on Bornholm can be seen as locked-in, whereas it can be a challenge for BOFA to mobilise the craft ecosystem in Hephæstus.

The craft makers' view on the project can become a challenge when establishing the Living Lab, as some of the craft makers feel that the project of Hephæstus utilizes their knowledge and experiences in which they are not being "paid" for. It has also been mentioned by several craft makers that the number of offerings of e.g., projects, workshops, etc. on Bornholm is already too much, and that the Maker's Island Secretariat provides several of the same activities as Hephæstus.

Thereby, BOFA should be very careful when interacting with the craft ecosystem on Bornholm and make sure that the project of Hephæstus does not have a top-down approach on the ecosystem as it will increase the resistance of network towards the project.

6. Conclusion

The activities carried out in task 5.1 has made it evident that there is already an established network in the craft ecosystem of Bornholm. The stakeholders and actors being a part of the network are all important to include in the process of the Living Lab. Different activities has shown that the craft ecosystem on Bornholm face different challenges, whereas some of the innovations and solutions to be developed and tested in Hephæstus and the Living Lab should target some of these challenges for the craft ecosystem on Bornholm to feel included and heard. It is important that Hephæstus does not have a top-down approach as it will create tension and increase the resistance towards the project in the craft ecosystem on Bornholm.

Future activities contributing to the establishment of the network participating at the Green Living Lab

Related project objectives

- Develop new sustainable business models for the craft sector
- Exploring visions for the future of craft integrating emerging technologies and contributing to a Circular Economy
- Establish a green living lab for Testing the Hephaestus innovation
- Combine cutting-edge technologies with craft material and processes through a craft-technology driven innovation methodology
- Develop lifelong learning methodology and a set of innovative curricula to equip craft-makers with diverse skillsets for innovation
- To design and operationalise a bespoke dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy.

Figure 10: Future activities contributing to the establishment of the networks participating at the Green Living Lab

7. Bibliography

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8. Appendix

Program for the event:

9:00-9:10	1. Welcome
9:10-10:05	2. Presentation of HEPHÆSTUS a. BOFA's and Bornholm's role – Bornholm as a Living Lab b. D20 Art Lab: "Atmospheres of Craft" <i>Questions</i>
10:05-10:20	3. Living Labs – what is it?
10:20-10:30	Break
10:30-12:00	4. Workshop sessions in groups a. Mapping: Challenges in the craft sector b. Brainstorming and ideation: Wishes for the project and the future
12:00-12:30	5. Lunch, networking and thank you for today